

NEXT GENERATION TRIGGERS ML OPTIMIZATION: QUANTIZATION TECHNIQUES FOR SCALABLE INFERENCE

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The project is carried out within the context of CERN's Next Generation Trigger (NGT)

project, where machine learning models are increasingly used to process large data streams under strict resource and latency constraints. Running such models efficiently on resource-limited hardware, particularly FPGAs, requires advanced optimization methods.

The objectives of this internship project are threefold:

1. **Research state-of-the-art quantization techniques:** Study the theoretical concepts behind quantization, conduct a detailed survey of quantization methods, including symmetric and asymmetric quantization, weight-only, dynamic range, mixed precision, and full-integer approaches, and assess their relevance to high-throughput environments.
2. **Assess and document the quantization methods and their implementation:** Analyze the trade-offs between accuracy, model compression, and inference speed, with a focus on their applicability to the NGT related use-cases. The findings are organized into a structured report that consolidates the theory, benefits, and limitations of each technique.
3. **Design automated tooling for quantization and integration with the NGT ML platform `ngt.cern.ch`:** Implement an automated workflow where users can upload models, apply quantization strategies, and retrieve quantized artifacts alongside logs, compression plots, and structured metadata. The integration within the NGT ML platform demonstrates how quantization can become part of CERN's larger trigger optimization framework.

The project is done within the CERN IT-CD-PI group, under the supervision of Amine Lahouel and Section Leader Ricardo Rocha. The expected outcome is a comprehensive understanding of quantization techniques, an evaluation of the available implementations in the major frameworks, along with a functional prototype of their integration into the NGT ML platform `ngt.cern.ch`, paving the way for more advanced customization and FPGA-oriented deployment in future work.

ABSTRACT

This project surveys state-of-the-art quantization techniques for machine learning models and evaluates how they can be applied to enable low-latency, high-throughput inference on resource-constrained hardware such as FPGAs within CERN's Next Generation Trigger (NGT) context. While these methods are generally platform-agnostic, our aim is to understand their trade-offs and integration within our machine learning platform.

The work is structured around three core tasks: (1) researching and summarizing SOTA quantization techniques (e.g., symmetric/asymmetric, weight-only, dynamic range, mixed precision, and full-integer methods); (2) understanding, analyzing, and presenting these techniques with an emphasis on accuracy–compression–latency trade-offs relevant to NGT; and (3) developing a PoC showcasing the integration of such techniques into the NGT ML platform `ngt.cern.ch`, which demonstrates an automated Kubeflow workflow where users can upload a model, select a quantization strategy, and obtain a quantized version together with logs, compression plots, and structured metadata.

The project establishes a foundation for enabling automated quantization workflows at CERN. Future work will focus on adding more quantization techniques, enhancing customization (e.g., calibration methods, per-layer precision, high-granularity quantization), and moving toward production-grade deployment within the NGT infrastructure. In doing so, this research bridges the gap between general-purpose quantization methods and their specialized application for FPGA-based real-time inference at CERN.

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1 Introduction

Machine learning models have become central to a wide range of scientific and industrial applications, including the real-time data processing pipelines used at CERN. In particular, the Next Generation Trigger (NGT) system aims to integrate machine learning–based decision making within high-throughput environments, where both inference speed and resource usage are critical. However, the size and complexity of modern state-of-the-art models make them difficult to deploy in such settings without significant optimization.

Recent advances in model design have produced architectures with billions of parameters. For example, DeepSeek V2 includes 236 billion parameters, which in standard FP32 representation requires nearly 472 GB of memory. Clearly, such models cannot be deployed directly on most hardware platforms, and certainly not on resource-constrained environments such as FPGAs that form part of the NGT project. Beyond memory requirements, floating-point arithmetic itself is relatively slow and energy-hungry compared to integer operations, which limits throughput and increases operational costs.

The aim of this project is therefore to study state-of-the-art quantization approaches, understand their trade-offs, and demonstrate their application through integration with the NGT platform. In particular, this report explores the theoretical underpinnings of quantization, surveys the main techniques in use, and presents a proof-of-concept implementation on KubeFlow that is integrated into `ngt.cern.ch`, allowing automated application of quantization strategies to machine learning models. In doing so, it sets the stage for the deployment of efficient, low-latency inference solutions on FPGAs and other resource-constrained hardware.

1.1 Why Should We Even Quantize?

The motivation for applying quantization techniques arises from the fundamental limitations of modern deep learning models. State-of-the-art architectures are not only large in terms of parameters but also expensive to deploy because they rely on floating-point arithmetic. This leads to two key challenges: *memory footprint* and *computational efficiency*.

Memory Limitations. Large models require an enormous amount of storage, often making deployment infeasible on devices with constrained resources. For example, models trained in FP32 format require four bytes per parameter, and when scaled to billions of parameters, the resulting size can reach hundreds of gigabytes. This scale is incompatible with FPGAs and other specialized accelerators used within CERN’s Next Generation Triggers (NGT) project.

Floating-Point Computation Costs. Even when models can be stored, inference is often slowed by floating-point computations, which are inherently slower and more energy-intensive compared to integer operations. Integer arithmetic is natively supported by most hardware, allowing much faster execution with reduced power consumption. For this reason, even general-purpose computers prefer integer calculations whenever possible.

Quantization as a Solution. Quantization addresses both of these challenges by mapping floating-point values into lower-precision integer representations. This process reduces storage requirements and accelerates computation, thereby enabling the deployment of large models in constrained environments. For instance, the DeepSeek example demonstrates how quantization can reduce model size from 472 GB (FP32) to only 40–60 GB (INT8), making previously impractical models usable in real-world settings.

Figure 1: Quantization reduces model size and computation cost, enabling deployment in resource-constrained environments.

Conclusion. Without quantization, many modern AI models remain impractical for deployment in real-time, resource-constrained environments such as those at CERN. Quantization is therefore not only an optimization technique but a requirement for scalability, efficiency, and feasibility in the NGT context.

2 What is Quantization?

At its core, quantization is the process of mapping values from a large set to a smaller set. In the context of machine learning, this typically involves reducing numerical precision, such as converting 32-bit floating-point values into 8-bit integers. The key idea is to represent the same information with fewer bits, thereby reducing storage requirements and computation cost.

2.1 An Intuitive Analogy

A simple analogy can be drawn from grading systems. Imagine a teacher who normally grades students out of 100 but suddenly decides to grade out of 10. A score of 97 would become 9, and a score of 91 would also map to 9. Although some fine distinctions are lost, the overall performance is still captured, but in a more compact form. This is exactly how quantization works: values are grouped into “buckets,” making them easier and faster to handle.

Figure 2: Visualisation of Mapping.

2.2 Quantization in Neural Networks

In neural networks, quantization is applied to numerical values such as *weights*, *biases*, and sometimes *activations*. Normally, these parameters are stored as floating-point numbers, which are expensive in terms of both memory and computation. By converting them into integers, it is possible to achieve significant reductions in model size and execution time, while maintaining accuracy close to that of the original model.

- Neural networks consist of various types of layers, including linear and convolutional layers.
- Linear layers contain matrices of weights and biases, typically stored as floating-point values.
- Quantization replaces these floating-point values with integer representations.
- The goal is to minimize the loss of accuracy while achieving substantial efficiency gains.

Figure 3: Neural Network Architecture

3 Types of Quantization

Quantization can be categorized along different dimensions: numerical formulation, implementation method, and granularity of application. Each type provides different trade-offs between efficiency and accuracy.

3.1 Numerical Formulations: Symmetric vs. Asymmetric

In symmetric quantization, zero in floating-point maps directly to zero in the quantized range, and the scale factor is applied symmetrically across positive and negative values. This often simplifies hardware implementation but may reduce flexibility.

In asymmetric quantization, the mapping allows for a nonzero offset, meaning the quantized zero can represent a nonzero floating-point value. This improves representation for datasets or activations that are not centered around zero.

It allows to map a series of floating-point numbers in the range $[\beta, \alpha]$ into another in the range $[0, 2^n - 1]$. For example, by using 8 bits, we can represent floating-point numbers in the range $[0, 255]$

Figure 4: Asymmetric Quantization

It allows to map a series of floating-point numbers in the range $[-\alpha, \alpha]$ into another in the range $[-(2^{n-1} - 1), 2^{n-1} - 1]$. For example, by using 8 bits, we can represent floating-point numbers in the range $[-127, 127]$

Figure 5: Symmetric Quantization

3.2 Implementation Methods: PTQ vs. QAT

Post-Training Quantization (PTQ) applies quantization to a pre-trained model, compressing weights and biases before inference. This approach is fast and straightforward but can lead to accuracy drops if the model is highly sensitive.

Quantization-Aware Training (QAT) incorporates quantization effects during training. By simulating quantization through fake-quantization layers, the model can adapt to reduced precision. This typically yields better accuracy than PTQ, though it requires additional training effort.

Figure 6: Post-Training Quantization (PTQ) vs. Quantization-Aware Training (QAT)

3.3 Weight-Only, Dynamic Range, Mixed Precision, and Full Integer Quantization

Beyond the basic distinctions, several variations of quantization are widely used:

- **Weight-Only Quantization (WOQ):** Only weights are quantized; activations remain in floating-point. This balances accuracy and memory efficiency.
- **Dynamic Range Quantization (DRQ):** Weights are quantized to integers, but activations are quantized dynamically at inference. This provides significant size reduction with modest accuracy trade-offs.
- **Mixed Precision Quantization (MPQ):** Uses different precisions (e.g., INT8, INT4, FP16) for different parts of the model, balancing accuracy and efficiency.
- **Full Integer Quantization (FIQ):** Both weights and activations are quantized to integers, enabling fully integer-based inference, ideal for hardware accelerators and edge devices.

3.4 Granularity: Per-Tensor vs. Per-Channel vs. Per-Weight

Another distinction is the granularity at which quantization parameters are applied. In per-tensor quantization, a single scale and zero-point are used for the entire tensor (e.g., a full weight matrix). This is simple and efficient but less accurate when values vary significantly across channels.

In per-channel quantization, each channel (e.g., convolution filter) has its own scale and zero-point. While this increases complexity and metadata, it typically improves accuracy for convolutional models.

Cutting-edge research at CERN is exploring even finer granularity through per-weight quantization, where each individual weight parameter can have its own precision level. High Granularity Quantization (HGQ) is an innovative gradient-based automatic bitwidth optimization algorithm that allows for mixed-precision quantization at arbitrary granularity, up to per-weight and per-activation level.

4 Applying Quantization

Once the basic principles of quantization are understood, the next step is to examine how it is applied in practice. The process generally follows a sequence of steps that transform a pre-trained floating-point model into a more compact quantized version.

4.1 Workflow

The typical quantization workflow begins with a model trained in FP32 precision. Depending on the chosen method (e.g., PTQ or QAT), the following steps are performed:

1. **Calibration:** Representative data samples are used to estimate the range of activations, which helps determine appropriate scale factors and zero-points.
2. **Quantization:** Model weights (and optionally activations) are mapped from FP32 to a lower-precision format such as INT8.
3. **Evaluation:** The quantized model is evaluated on validation data to measure accuracy and latency trade-offs.
4. **Deployment:** The final quantized model is exported for use on the target hardware (e.g., FPGA).

Figure 7: General workflow for applying quantization to a neural network model.

4.2 Trade-Offs: Compression vs. Performance

Quantization is not without cost. By reducing precision, multiple floating-point values may map to the same integer value. This is a direct consequence of the pigeonhole principle: when compressing a large set of possible values into a smaller set, some distinctions are inevitably lost. The challenge is to determine how much compression can be applied before the accuracy of the model deteriorates to unacceptable levels.

Figure 8: Compression–performance trade-off: finding the sweet spot where models remain efficient yet accurate.

4.3 Conclusion

Applying quantization is therefore a balancing act. It requires careful calibration and evaluation to ensure that the resulting model is small enough to meet resource constraints while still preserving the accuracy needed for high-energy particle physics related tasks within the NGT project.

5 Frameworks and Tooling

Several machine learning frameworks provide built-in support for quantization, enabling researchers and practitioners to compress and optimize models with minimal additional effort. These frameworks differ in their supported quantization techniques, deployment backends, and hardware integration.

5.1 PyTorch

PyTorch provides extensive support for both Post-Training Quantization (PTQ) and Quantization-Aware Training (QAT). It includes calibration tools, observer modules, and fake quantization layers that allow developers to simulate low-precision arithmetic during training. PyTorch also supports exporting quantized models for deployment on hardware accelerators.

5.2 TensorFlow Lite

TensorFlow Lite offers quantization options through its TFLite Converter. It supports both PTQ and QAT, enabling the deployment of smaller and faster models on edge devices such as mobile phones and embedded systems. TensorFlow Lite quantization is widely adopted in real-world applications due to its strong integration with Android and microcontroller platforms.

5.3 ONNX Runtime

The ONNX Runtime provides a framework-agnostic approach to quantization, supporting dynamic, static, and QAT quantization. This makes it possible to optimize models trained in PyTorch, TensorFlow, or other frameworks and deploy them on a variety of hardware backends. ONNX quantization is particularly useful for cross-platform compatibility.

5.4 Comparison

While all three frameworks provide mechanisms for applying quantization, their strengths differ. PyTorch is widely used for research and prototyping, TensorFlow Lite excels at mobile and embedded deployment, and ONNX Runtime ensures interoperability across hardware and frameworks. Together, they provide a comprehensive toolbox for applying quantization in diverse scenarios, including the needs of the NGT project at CERN.

6 Results

The effectiveness of quantization was evaluated experimentally using both PyTorch and TensorFlow frameworks. Each framework provided a different perspective on how quantization affects model size, latency, and accuracy. The results are presented in terms of model architectures, compression ratios, inference latency, and accuracy retention.

6.1 PyTorch Results

Model Architecture. The experiments in PyTorch were carried out on a simplified LargeCNN architecture consisting of convolutional, batch normalization, ReLU, and pooling layers, followed by fully connected layers and an output classifier.

Figure 9: LargeCNN architecture used for PyTorch quantization experiments.

Size, Latency, and Compression. A comparison was made between FP32, Dynamic Range Quantization (DRQ), Post-Training Quantization (PTQ), and Quantization-Aware Training (QAT). Figure ?? summarizes the impact on model size, latency per batch, latency per sample, and percentage size reduction.

Method	Bits	Size(MB)	ms/batch	ms/sample	Size Red.(%)
FP32	32	1.09	248.61	0.994	0.0
DRQ (Linear)	8(int8)	0.34	213.86	0.855	68.5
PTQ Static	8(int8)	0.29	120.96	0.484	73.9
QAT int8	8(int8)	0.29	121.62	0.486	73.9

Figure 10: PyTorch results: comparison of FP32, DRQ, PTQ, and QAT models in terms of size, latency, and compression.

Latency per Sample. The per-sample inference latency is shown in Figure ??, where quantized models (PTQ and QAT) demonstrate substantial improvements compared to the FP32 baseline.

6.2 TensorFlow Results

Model Architecture. For TensorFlow experiments, a deep CNN architecture was used with multiple convolutional blocks, pooling layers, and a dense head.

Model Size Comparison. Quantization significantly reduced model size compared to FP32. Dynamic quantization achieved compression factors of up to 12 \times , while FP16 quantization provided around 6 \times compression. These results are illustrated in Figure ??.

Figure 11: Inference latency per sample for PyTorch models under different quantization strategies.

Figure 12: CNN architecture used for TensorFlow quantization experiments.

Inference Latency. Latency decreased with quantization, particularly with float16 and dynamic quantization. The results are shown in Figure ??, where reductions of up to 3× were observed compared to FP32.

Accuracy. Despite compression and latency gains, accuracy was largely preserved. Both dynamic and float16 quantization retained performance close to the FP32 baseline, as illustrated in Figure ??.

Compression Ratios. Compression ratios with respect to the original FP32 model size are summarized in Figure ??, confirming that quantization enables storage savings of up to 12×.

6.3 Summary of Results

The PyTorch and TensorFlow experiments confirm that quantization delivers substantial memory savings and latency improvements, while maintaining accuracy within acceptable margins. These findings validate quantization as a key enabler for deploying machine learning models on resource-constrained hardware in the NGT project.

Figure 13: TensorFlow model size comparison: FP32 vs dynamic quantization vs float16 quantization.

Figure 14: Inference time for TensorFlow models: original vs quantized.

Figure 15: Accuracy comparison of original TensorFlow model and quantized versions.

Figure 16: Compression ratio relative to FP32 model size under different quantization schemes in TensorFlow.

7 Discussion

Quantization brings clear benefits for deploying machine learning models in resource-constrained environments such as CERN's Next Generation Trigger (NGT) project. The main advantages observed are:

- **Reduced model size:** Lower precision reduces memory footprint, making large models feasible to store and deploy.
- **Faster inference:** Integer arithmetic executes more efficiently than floating-point, leading to improved latency.
- **Hardware compatibility:** Quantization aligns with the capabilities of accelerators such as FPGAs, which favor simpler integer operations.

However, these advantages come with challenges. The most important limitation is the *accuracy drop* that can occur when too much information is lost in the mapping from FP32 to INT8 (or lower). Calibration strategies and advanced methods such as per-channel quantization and mixed precision help mitigate this issue, but the trade-off remains fundamental.

Another consideration specific to FPGAs is resource utilization. Different quantization methods affect FPGA resources such as Look-Up Tables (LUTs), Digital Signal Processors (DSPs), and Block RAM (BRAM). Achieving efficient deployment requires balancing accuracy, compression, and hardware footprint. These trade-offs must be carefully studied in the NGT context, where both throughput and physics relevance are non-negotiable.

✓ Pros	⚠ Cons
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduces model size (e.g., 8x-12x smaller) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slight accuracy drop
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speeds up inference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires calibration/fine-tuning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables deployment on edge devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not work well on all architectures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saves energy and memory bandwidth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some quantization methods are complex

Figure 17: Pros and cons of quantization.

8 NGT ML Platform Integration

In addition to surveying quantization techniques, this project implemented a proof-of-concept pipeline on Kubeflow, integrated into `ngt.cern.ch`. The goal of this pipeline is to automate the application of quantization strategies to machine learning models, providing a reproducible and user-friendly workflow.

8.1 Pipeline Design

The pipeline consists of modular components that perform the following steps:

1. Upload a pre-trained model to the platform.
2. Select a quantization strategy (e.g., dynamic quantization or weight-only quantization).
3. Apply quantization automatically to the model.
4. Generate logs, plots, and structured JSON metadata describing the run.
5. Store the quantized model for retrieval and deployment.

(a) Kubeflow pipeline DAG with dynamic and weight-only quantization components.

```

(base) nsadek@q-draft4-0:/share$ ls
dynamic_compression_ratio.png  dynamic_quant_log.json  dynamic_size_comparison.png  model_dynamic_sd.pth  resnet18_fp32_sd.pth
(base) nsadek@q-draft4-0:/share$
  
```

(b) Output folder with quantized models, plots, and logs.

```

plt.ylabel("FP32 size / Quant size (x)")
plt.title("Compression ratio")
plt.xticks(rotation=0)
for i, v in enumerate(df.set_index("name")["compression_ratio"]):
    if pd.notna(v):
        plt.text(i, v, f"{v:.2f}x", ha="center", va="bottom", fontsize=9)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
  
```

Parsed log summary:

name	input mb	output mb	compression ratio	linear pre	linear post dynamic	conv2d wrapped
0 dynamic	44.667	43.203	1.0339	1	1	None

(c) Notebook visualization of size comparison and compression ratio plots.

```

{
  "ok": true,
  "message": "dynamic quantization completed",
  "env": {
    "torch": "2.3.1+cu121",
    "torchvision": "0.18.1+cu121"
  },
  "paths": {
    "input_state_dict": "/shared/resnet18_fp32_sd.pth",
    "output_state_dict": "/shared/model_dynamic_sd.pth",
    "size_plot": "/shared/dynamic_size_comparison.png",
    "ratio_plot": "/shared/dynamic_compression_ratio.png"
  },
  "sizes": {
    "input_bytes": 46836268,
    "input_mb": 44.667,
    "output_bytes": 45301114,
    "output_mb": 43.203,
    "compression_ratio": 1.0339
  },
  "layers": {
    "linear_pre": 1,
    "linear_post_dynamic": 1
  },
  "timing_sec": {
    "load_and_rebuild": 0.2504,
    "quantize_dynamic": 0.0185,
    "total": 0.8818
  }
}
  
```

(d) Example of structured JSON log with environment, paths, sizes, and timing.

Figure 18: Artifacts produced by the Kubeflow quantization pipeline: pipeline graph, outputs, notebook visualizations, and structured JSON logs.

9 Future Work

While the current work establishes a foundation for applying quantization to machine learning models within the NGT context, several directions remain open for further development and refinement.

9.1 Balancing Accuracy and FPGA Resources

A key open question is how far quantization can be pushed without degrading accuracy on physics-relevant signals. Different quantization strategies affect FPGA resource usage in distinct ways, particularly in terms of Look-Up Tables (LUTs), Digital Signal Processors (DSPs), and Block RAM (BRAM). Future research will focus on characterizing these trade-offs and identifying optimal strategies for deployment in NGT.

9.2 Extending Quantization Techniques

Currently, the KubeFlow pipeline supports a basic set of quantization strategies. A natural extension is to incorporate additional techniques, such as:

- Lower-precision formats (e.g., INT4, FP16 hybrids).
- Percentile-based calibration methods to handle outliers more robustly.
- Layer-specific quantization to provide different precision for different parts of the model.

These additions will allow the platform to capture a broader range of accuracy–efficiency trade-offs.

9.3 Customization and User Control

Another priority is to increase customization options within the NGT ML platform `ngt.cern.ch` interface. Instead of a one-size-fits-all approach, users will be able to select:

- The quantization method (PTQ, QAT, WOQ, DRQ, MPQ, FIQ).
- Calibration strategy (min–max vs. percentile-based).
- Precision level on a per-layer basis.

This flexibility will make the platform adaptable to a wide variety of models and use cases.

9.4 Integration within NGT Infrastructure

Future development will also focus on strengthening integration with the NGT infrastructure. The goal is to enable end-to-end workflows where models can be trained, quantized, and deployed on FPGA hardware directly through the platform. This would transform the current proof-of-concept into a production-grade service for the CERN research community.

9.5 Summary

In summary, future work will expand both the technical scope and usability of the quantization pipeline: adding new techniques, enabling fine-grained customization, and embedding the pipeline within CERN's operational workflows. These developments will support the broader goal of deploying efficient, low-latency machine learning inference on FPGA hardware at scale.

10 Conclusion

This project set out to investigate and integrate quantization techniques for machine learning models with the goal of enabling deployment on resource-constrained hardware such as FPGAs within CERN's Next Generation Trigger (NGT) project. The work was structured around three main tasks:

1. **Researching state-of-the-art quantization methods:** A survey of symmetric and asymmetric quantization, PTQ and QAT, as well as WOQ, DRQ, MPQ, and FIQ was conducted to understand the theoretical foundations and trade-offs of each technique.
2. **Understanding and presenting these methods:** The strengths and limitations of each approach were analyzed with respect to accuracy, compression, and performance, particularly in the context of FPGA resource constraints.
3. **Developing a Kubeflow proof-of-concept pipeline:** An automated workflow was implemented and integrated into the NGT ML platform `ngt.cern.ch`, allowing models to be uploaded, quantized using different strategies, and accompanied by logs, compression plots, and structured metadata.

The results confirm that quantization significantly reduces model size and improves inference efficiency, while careful calibration ensures that accuracy remains within acceptable limits. These findings demonstrate the potential of quantization as a critical enabler for scalable machine learning inference in high-throughput environments.

By integrating quantization workflows into the NGT ML platform `ngt.cern.ch`, this project lays the groundwork for automated and reproducible optimization of models destined for FPGA deployment. Looking forward, the pipeline can be extended with additional quantization techniques, customization options, and deeper integration into NGT infrastructure. In this way, quantization becomes not only a research focus but also a practical tool to support the future of real-time data processing at CERN.

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